

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PROPER PRONUNCIATION IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This study aims to find out how students view pronunciation and its significance in spoken English. The study was motivated by the declining popularity of pronunciation in the ESL setting, which has resulted in a dearth of efforts to enhance learners' pronunciation abilities despite widespread concern among professionals working in fields that need understandable spoken English. In particular, the study examined how students perceive several aspects of correct English pronunciation. Survey questionnaires were used in the study to collect data, and SPSS and factor analysis were used for statistical analysis of the data. Overall, the results indicated that the respondents understood the importance of proper pronunciation in spoken English.*

Keywords: *L2 learners, accurate pronunciation, spoken English, frequency.*

Introduction

In both productive and receptive communication, proper pronunciation is crucial. Regarding their comfort level in oral communication, L2 learners frequently express anxiety (Bang, 1999). Although it is feasible for an L2 student to put on an excellent show, because it operates at a subconscious level, it is frequently difficult to change (Munro & Derwing, 2008). Native listeners are able to resolve ambiguity when a pronunciation element makes a word difficult to understand. On the other hand, non-native listeners who may rely more on the auditory signal are vulnerable to communication failure (Harper, 2004).

However, given that L2 learners use English more frequently among non-native speakers than among native speakers (Jenkins, 2000), most frequently in Malaysian educational and professional settings, L2 learners may still need to master the simpler suprasegmental qualities of English rather than the complex segmental sounds for mutual intelligibility. Such restrictions among L2 speakers can be annoying and may require attention. Pronunciation instruction is crucial for L2 learners in the context of

interactions with both non-native speakers and native speakers in general. However, if the learners do not recognize the significance of such demands, training to enhance pronunciation may be useless.

More than 80% of the trainees in Rajadurai's (2001) study on the attitudes and concerns for appropriate English pronunciation among a group of Malaysian ESL teacher trainees felt that pronunciation is a key component of spoken English. This discovery may be predicted, given that they are English professors. Another research conducted in a non-Malay environment found that trainees had genuine concerns about the precision of their segmental pronunciation (Dalton & Seidlhofer, 2000). Although it has been argued that pronunciation is the hardest talent to master, several experts (Roach, 1991; CelceMurcia, Brinton & Goodwind, 1996; Dalton & Seidlhofer, 2000) asserted that learners would normally wish to enhance their pronunciation.

The purpose of this study is to investigate how students view pronunciation and its significance in spoken English. The level of awareness and concerns for improvement among the students are also of relevance to this study. This is accomplished by outlining the aspects and factors necessary to comprehend language learners' perceptions of the significance of accurate pronunciation in spoken English.

Materials and Methodology

To gather information on learners' judgments of appropriate English pronunciation, a series of survey questions was used. Therefore, some of the respondents were interviewed to extract details on the causes and explanations of their viewpoints in order to further substantiate the data gathered through the survey. It is hoped that the results would help to shed some light on key factors to take into account while creating a supportive atmosphere and teaching strategy for English language learners. The study included about 300 secondary-level students ($n=300$) from a randomly chosen school in the states of Johor, Kelantan, and Selangor (one from an urban and one from a rural school in each state, $n=50$). A set of survey questions with 33 items was distributed to all participating pupils.

To confirm the relevance of student judgments on the significance of pronunciation in spoken English, data from the survey questionnaire was statistically analyzed using SPSS. To achieve the study's goals, the researcher performed a variety of statistical tests, including frequency, mean, standard deviation, and factor analysis. The demographic features of the respondents are first examined using frequency. Second, based on the expectations of the respondents, the means of the 33 replies to the

assessment of the significance of pronunciation were computed. Third, factor analysis was used to determine the underlying aspects of the students' judgments of the significance of proper pronunciation in spoken English. Using Cronbach's alpha, each variable for each component obtained was computed to assess its reliability.

Results

This study's overarching goal is to learn more about how students view pronunciation and its significance in spoken English. Additionally, it aims to identify the factors that influence students' perception. A collection of survey questionnaires was the primary tool utilized to elicit their perceptions. The questionnaire was divided into two main sections: the students' demographic information and their opinions on the significance of pronunciation in spoken English. 30 students from the same population participated in a pilot research to test the instrument and refine the survey questions. For part 2, the tool uses a five-point Likert scale to assess students' impressions. The real study did not, however, use the same pupils. The reliability test criteria is met by the 33-item questionnaire's Cronbach alpha, which is 0.810, as shown in Table 1. All of the reverse-coded survey questions were taken into consideration when doing the Cronbach alpha test.

Discussion

The results of this study show that students have a favorable attitude toward the significance of proper pronunciation in spoken English. *Pertanika J. Soc. Sci. & Hum.* 23 (S): 143-158 (2015). This is in line with earlier research's conclusions. For instance, Steed and Delicado Cantero (2014) found a similar pattern in their research of Spanish students learning English in Australia, with the Spanish students displaying a favorable attitude regarding the significance of proper pronunciation in spoken English. They asserted that further measures should be done to raise students' awareness of the value of proper pronunciation and that effective educational methods should be taken into consideration to teach pronunciation.

Conclusion

The study's findings were intended to help identify crucial requirements for assisting students in developing positive attitudes and perceptions about proper pronunciation in spoken English. The component suggested in this study as a result of the findings may have implications for how teachers evaluate and forecast their students' perceptions, particularly with regard to the significance of pronunciation in spoken English. Therefore, it is a sensible move for English language trainers and teachers

to take into account the dimensions as a set of boosters in assuring successful outcomes for a certain English class or intense English program.

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